

FORMING A CULTURE OF BUSINESS COMMUNICATION AT A TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY IN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE CLASSES

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Annotation

The transition to market relations has changed the requirements for the level of preparedness of specialists in technical universities. So, along with competencies in their specialty, the ability to negotiate in the field of business began to be presented to a specialist. This article is devoted to the substantiation of this problem in a higher technical educational institution when teaching the Russian language.

Keywords: Higher Educational Institution, Technical, Labor Market, Development of Society, Culture of Business Communication, Analysis, Specificity, Pedagogical Conditions.

INTRODUCTION

The transition to a market economy, changes in the socio-cultural sphere actualize the problem of training students of a technical university in accordance with the requirements of the labor market, impose new criteria on the quality of education of future specialists, on the structure and content of the educational process. The social, organizational and pedagogical request of society aimed at the development of the creative potential of the individual in higher educational institutions, the formation of scientific and methodological support and information and educational environment, search for solutions to the problems of professional and pedagogical creativity based on the analysis of the educational components of activity (Benchmarking), the Bologna process, with its focus on the practical orientation of training, integrated management of the quality of education (Total quality management), improvement of intellectualized education systems based on general professional and special competencies (Tuning) associated with the use of modern didactic means are identified as a priority problem of forming a culture of business communication during the preparation of students at the university.

An analysis of the situation of social development in our country indicates the need of society for the formation of a modern culture of business communication among future specialists of a technical university, which requires the approval of civilized forms of business communication.

For full communication of people during business meetings in the process of work, belonging to various linguistic and cultural communities, a certain stock of "background knowledge" is needed, without which it is impossible to establish contact with subsequent business relations in the future. When teaching a non-native language, it is necessary to take into account the specifics of the specialist's field of activity, since language is a means of integrating the entire mental content of human consciousness, cultural, social, historical, business and other values.

That is why familiarization with the culture of the native speaker of the language (Russian) should be formed among Uzbek students regarding a holistic view of the national and cultural norms of communication, in particular business communication.

The educational system of countries such as the USA, Europe, South Korea, China, Singapore, and Japan is the leader in the world ranking on the use of new pedagogical strategies in education. Therefore, it is important that the specialists of the leading universities included in the TOP-1000 stand out in the international labor market for their competitiveness, the necessary competencies in the specialty and the ability to establish business contacts with partners from other countries.

LITERATURE AND METHODOLOGY

The study on the formation of communicative competence of business communication of students of a technical university in the Russian language classes is based on the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-4947 dated February 7, 2017 "On the Action Strategy for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-3907 dated August 14, 2017 "Education of young people spiritually, morally and physically, their education - on measures to raise the quality of the education system by new level", Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on October 8, 2019 No. PP-5847 "On approval of the concept for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 29, 2020 No. PP-6097 "On approval of the Concept for the development of science until 2030", Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 6, 2019 No. PP-5812 dated "On additional measures to further improve the system of professional education Education", Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PP-2909 dated April 20, 2017 "On measures for the further development of the higher education system", Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 5, 2018 PQ-3775 "On additional measures to improve the quality of education in higher education institutions and ensure their active participation in comprehensive reforms implemented in the country", Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 27, 2017 PQ-3151 "On measures to further expand the participation of areas and sectors of the economy in improving the quality of training of highly educated specialists", Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 19, 2021 PP-5117 "On measures to bring activities to popularize the study of foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a qualitatively new level", as well as other regulatory documents related to pedagogical activity.

On the problem of studying the formation of the culture of Russian business communication, Russian scientists such as Zverintsev A.B., Kurbatov V.I., Panfilova A.P. and others were engaged. It should be noted that so far no special studies have been conducted on the formation of the communicative competence of a specialist of another nationality in the study of a foreign language, including verbal and non-verbal means of communication. The works of R.N. Botavin, F.A. Kuzin, V. N. Lavrinenko reveal the essence of the ethics of business behavior that form the modern culture of business communication in Russian culture. The culture of

Russian speech communication in relation to objects such as philosophy, logic, psychology, sociology and ethics was considered in their works by I.A. Malkhanova, L.A. Vvedenskaya, H. Lemmerman, Soper Paul L., V.E. Chernyavskaya, E.N. Zaretskaya and others. Nochevnik, E. V. Rudensky, L.G. Titova, M.I. Chekhovskikh and others conducted research on the disclosure of the content of social and psychological processes in business communication and the analysis of the system model of business communication among the Russian-speaking population. Another group of scientists such as G.G. Zaitsev, R.D. Lewis, G.M. Shelamov, N.B. Enkelman and others determined the criteria for the success of Russian business communication, the formation of professional competencies in the field of business career, corresponding to a certain level of culture of business communication.

An analysis of the studied literature has shown that studies of this issue on the formation of a culture of business communication among Uzbek students of a technical university in Russian language classes and the creation of special pedagogical conditions for teaching in higher technical education are completely absent and are waiting for their solution.

OUTCOMES

The social development of our country is directly related to the export of our products. Uzbekistan is actively developing its trade relations with all neighboring countries and far abroad. Trade relations with the Russian state are developing every year. The expansion of trade relations in all spheres testifies to the need of society for the formation of a modern culture of business communication in Russian language among technical specialists. Future specialists of a technical university should learn in the learning process civilized forms of business communication adopted in Russian society for the successful achievement of an agreement in the business sphere.

For full communication of people during business meetings in the process of work, belonging to various linguistic and cultural communities, a certain stock of "background knowledge" is needed, without which it is impossible to establish contact with subsequent business relations in the future. When teaching a non-native language, it is necessary to take into account the specifics of the specialist's field of activity, since language is a means of integrating the entire mental content of human consciousness, cultural, social, and historical and other values. That is why the introduction to the culture of the native speaker of the language (Russian) should be understood as the formation of a relatively holistic view of the national and cultural norms of communication, in particular business communication, among Uzbek students.

The need for a high level of the formed culture of business communication among engineers, which is part of their professional competence, is confirmed by the result of a survey of employers conducted as part of the study.

For an effective process of forming a culture of business communication among engineering students during the training period, a set of pedagogical conditions is necessary that contribute to the creation of a modern holographic learning model with a synergistic effect, while academic disciplines are built into a system logical cyclic-modular system, which, by

expanding the content of education and using innovative technologies, creates the foundation for a culture of business communication.

Therefore, to solve this problem, it is necessary to solve the following research tasks:

- To clarify the essence and structure of the modern culture of business communication in accordance with the specifics of the engineer's profession;
- To develop a conceptual model of the modern culture of business communication, which is in demand for an engineer, to determine the indicators and criteria for its forcing among engineering students, on its basis to design a pedagogical model for the formation of a culture of business communication in the process of studying at a university;
- To justify the choice of pedagogical conditions and to develop structural and content components of the educational process aimed at creating a culture of business communication;
- To simulate a holographic training system with a synergistic effect through the creation of a cyclic-modular program, to experimentally prove its effectiveness;
- To create on the basis of the study educational and methodical literature that forms a culture of business communication among engineering students.
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According to the pedagogical theories of world scientists, teachers and practitioners, in the formation of students' readiness for professional activity in higher professional education, the continuity, consistency and relevance of education, the effectiveness of the educational system, taking into account the pedagogy-psychological, economic, social and individual capabilities of the student, the different types of education used, the methods that are inextricably linked with the created creative environment and educational space for the full realization of the hidden abilities of students. This means that it is necessary to ensure the continuity of teaching in market conditions, knowledge of business etiquette, the development of the learning process and the content of the subject of the Russian language with a focus on the formation of practical skills in business communication in Russian language.

DISCUSSION

The formation of communicative competence, a culture of business communication among engineers, Uzbek students in Russian language classes is necessary, since it will serve to increase the level of professional activity of a specialist engineer in work. This material incorporates information on speech etiquette, which will not only acquaint students with the national-linguistic picture of the world, will provide full communication in Russian language. Implementation of the delivered The goal requires taking into account the ethno-cultural and linguistic knowledge of non-Russian students, to determine the nature of the national and cultural specifics of the student audience, to identify the difficulties of assimilating realities with the national and cultural characteristics of business communication, to determine the principles of selection of educational material, to differentiate its volume in accordance with the goals of forming a national-linguistic picture of the world of bilingual students, to experimentally test the feasibility and effectiveness of the methodology for working with selected material in the educational process.

Consequently, the problems of creating pedagogical conditions that meet modern trends in the development of the labor market are relevant. It is due to insufficient development in pedagogical science, a number of typical contradictions characteristic of the modern educational practice of engineering students of a technical university:

- Between the importance of a practical focus on training specialists with a developed culture of business communication and the existing theoretical knowledge base on the subject without taking into account the modern realities of the dynamically developing Uzbek-Russian economic space;
- Between the important role played by the culture of business communication in the profession of a technical engineer, and the fact that there is no general concept of its formation at the university, the novelty of pedagogical conditions that contribute to its formation among future specialists;
- Between the need of the educational process to expand the content of education through the disciplines of the technological direction and subjects aimed at the formation of a competitive specialist and the ability to establish business contacts with partners from other countries;
- Between the fragmentation of the information of the norms on business communication and the limited time frame of the subject of the Russian language and the period of their development;
- Between the lack of a subject and methods of teaching business communication at the university, the lack of motivation of teachers to improve it and innovative pedagogical technologies that contribute to the modern level of proficiency in a foreign language (in our case, the Russian language).

Many years of experience at the university, as well as the requirements of employers, allows us to assert that research on the formation of communicative competence of the culture of business communication among engineering specialists can be used to create curricula and teaching aids, methodological recommendations for the formation of a higher national and cultural level among Uzbek students in Russian language classes.

CONCLUSION

Thus, in order to train a highly qualified and sought-after specialist in the labor market, it is necessary to form knowledge of the culture of business communication among future specialists. To do this, it is necessary to determine the scientific foundations of the culture of business communication and the creation of technology for its formation among students of a technical university, as well as to create a set of pedagogical conditions that meet the modern requirements of society for the quality of professional training of specialists in the production and sale of products. Therefore, it is necessary to implement the following recommendations:

- 1) To introduce into the practice of teaching the Russian language a specially developed system for determining the level of professional language competence of students in business communication.
- 2) Newly created teaching kits (textbooks for students) in the Russian language should be professionally oriented.
- 3) To achieve the goal of teaching the Russian language, it is necessary to actively introduce vocabulary for business communication in order to form the level of business communication and communicative competence.

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